

DERIVATION OF AN EQUATION FOR SLOW COAGULATION OF COLLOIDS ON THE BASIS OF SMOLUCHOWSKI'S THEORY

BY B. N. GHOSH

Assuming that ϵ in Smolachowski equation,

$$\Sigma n = \frac{n_0}{1 + \frac{t}{T} \epsilon}$$

for slow coagulation, is equal to $K/(1 + at)$ (where K and a are constants and t , the time measured from the start of coagulation), an equation has been deduced which can be tested by direct counting of n_0 and Σn in an ultramicroscope. The agreement between the observed values of Σn and those calculated from the equation is fair. With the same assumptions as above, combined with Rayleigh's equation for scattering of light by particles, an equation $D_t/D_i = (1 + bt)/(1 + at)$ has been deduced in which a and b are constants and D_i and D_t are the galvanometer deflections initially (*i.e.* at $t=0$) and after a time t respectively. The latter equation agrees satisfactorily with the experimental data.

It is generally accepted that in the region of rapid coagulation of colloids by electrolytes, the following equation of Smoluchowski holds good (Zsigmondy, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1917, 92, 600; Westgren and Reitstotter, *ibid.*, p. 750).

$$\Sigma n = \frac{n_0}{1 + \frac{t}{T}} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where Σn represents the sum of single, double, triple etc. particles per unit volume of the system after a time, t , following the addition of an electrolyte to the colloid, n_0 , the total number of particles initially present per unit volume, and T , a characteristic constant. For slow coagulation, this equation was found inadequate, and Smoluchowski therefore suggested a modified form of the above equation, expressed as:

$$\Sigma n = \frac{n_0}{1 + \frac{t}{T} \epsilon} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where ϵ represents the percentage of successful encounter of the approaching particles with the central one. The experimental results of Kruyt and Van Arkel (*Kolloid Z.*, 1923, 32, 29), Mukherjee and Mazumdar (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 785), Rai and Ghosh (*Kolloid Z.*, 1957, 154, 146) and others in the region of slow coagulation do not agree, except at the initial stages of coagulation, with this modified equation also. It appears that in equation (2), ϵ decreases as t increases. In some cases of slow coagulation, Σn ceases to decrease any further after some time. This fact can be accounted for broadly by assuming that

$$\epsilon = \frac{K}{1 + at} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

where K and a are constants.

Substituting this value of ϵ in equation (2), we get the following expression after simplification :

$$\frac{\sum n_k}{n_0} = \frac{1 + at}{1 + \beta t} \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

where a and β are constants and $\beta > a$.

Before proceeding further, it is necessary to examine whether the assumption made above, when introduced into the differential equation for the kinetics of coagulation, does lead to an expression of the same form as equation (2).

For rapid coagulation (vide Kruyt, "Colloid Science", 1952, Vol. I, p. 287) the differential equation can be written as :

$$\frac{d\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} n_k}{dt} = - 4\pi D_1 R \left(\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} n_k\right)^2 \dots \dots (5)$$

where R represents the radius of the sphere of attraction and is approximately twice the radius of a primary particle, and D , the diffusion constant.

For slow coagulation, introduction into equation (5) of the Smoluchowski factor, ϵ , a constant, leads to the expression :

$$\frac{d\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} n_k}{dt} = - 4\pi D_1 R \epsilon \left(\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} n_k\right)^2 \dots \dots (6)$$

Since the rate factor $4\pi D_1 R \epsilon$ decreases with time, it is assumed that ϵ alone is not constant but decreases with time. We may then write equation (6) as

$$\frac{d\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} n_k}{dt} = 4\pi D_1 R \frac{1}{a} \cdot \frac{d\epsilon}{dt} \left(\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} n_k\right)^2 \dots \dots (7)$$

That is, in place of ϵ in equation (6), we write $d\epsilon/dt$ and introduce a constant "1/a" in equation (7) for necessary adjustment. The solution of the differential equation (7) leads to the expression :

$$\sum n_k = \frac{n_0}{1 + \frac{t}{T} \epsilon}$$

when ϵ is put equal to $K/(1+at)$, as stated already. Therefore the assumption, we have made, does not lead to any incompatibility.

How far equation (4) is in agreement with the experimental data has been discussed herein.

Experimental Data and their Interpretation

Ultramicroscopic counting of particles of several selenium sols at different intervals of time, both in the regions of slow and rapid coagulation, was made by Kruyt

* The negative sign disappears because ϵ decreases with time.

and Van Arkel (*loc. cit.*). A few of their data for slow coagulation are recorded in Table I in which Σn_{obs} represents the number of particles found by ultramicroscopic counting after a time, t , following the addition of electrolyte to the colloid, and Σn_{calc} represents the corresponding number calculated from equation (4). For the evaluation of a and β in equation (4), a curve is drawn by plotting the observed values of Σn against t and then from known values of Σn and t , for two points in the curve, a and β are evaluated.

TABLE I

Selenium sol 17 C.

KCl = 50 mM/litre. $n_0 = 29.7 \times 10^9$ /c.c. Radius of particle = 52. $a = 0.022$. $\beta = 0.11$.

t (in hrs.)	0.66	4.25	19.0	43.0	73.0	167.0
$(\Sigma n_{obs}) \times 10^{-9}$	20.8	19.1	14.4	10.7	7.7	6.5
$(\Sigma n_{calc}) \times 10^{-9}$	28.0	20.4	13.7	10.1	8.5	7.2

KCl = 60 mM/litre. $n_0 = 29.7 \times 10^9$. $a = 0.3$. $\beta = 1.4$.

t (in hrs.)	0.25	0.83	1.5	19.5	49.5	144.0
$(\Sigma n_{obs}) \times 10^{-9}$	21.4	16.6	14.5	9.07	5.6	3.4
$(\Sigma n_{calc}) \times 10^{-9}$	23.4	17.2	13.9	7.2	6.7	6.5

Selenium sol 14A.

KCl = 30 mM/litre. $n_0 = 36.9 \times 10^9$. $a = 0.013$. $\beta = 0.74$. Radius = 62

t (in hrs.)	0.25	5.25	28.5	73.0	241.0	337.0
$(\Sigma n_{obs}) \times 10^{-9}$	35.0	33.3	22.3	13.82	14.3	13.9
$(\Sigma n_{calc}) \times 10^{-9}$	36.5	32.6	23.6	...	14.3	13.6

TABLE II

Arsenius sulphide sol.

$D_i = 124$. NaCl = $N/13$. $b = 0.006$. $a = 0.035$

t (in min.)	0	5	10	20	25	30	40
D_i obs	124	111	96.5	80	77	71	65.5
D_i calc	...	108.7	97.5	81.7	76.1	70.8	64.1

$D_i = 124$. NaCl = $N/11$. $b = 0.003$. $a = 0.2$.

t (in min.)	0	5	10	15.0	20.0	25.0	30.0	45.0	55.0	75.0
D_i obs	124	59	39	30.0	23.0	19.0	16.2	10.0	9.0	5.5
D_i calc	...	61	40	29.6	23.3	18.8	16.1	10.7	8.9	6.0

$D_i = 37$. $AlCl_3 = N/2,500$. $b = 0.2$. $a = 0.4$.

t (in min.)	0	2	4	6.8	16.4	26.8	37.3	53.0
D_i obs	37	28.5	25.6	23.8	21.3	20.5	20.0	19.0
D_i calc	...	28.7	25.6	23.5	21.0	20.1	19.7	19.3

In Table II are recorded the data taken from Fig. 1 and Fig. 3 of the paper of Mukherjee and Mazumdar (*loc. cit.*). In this table D_i represents the galvanometer deflection corresponding to the intensity I_i of the light transmitted through the glass cell of length L containing the colloid after a time, t , following the addition of electrolyte

to it and D_t , the deflection corresponding to intensity I_t of light transmitted through the colloid in the same cell at $t=0$, i.e., in the absence of electrolyte. Let D_0 represent the deflection corresponding to the intensity I_0 of light transmitted through water in the aforesaid cell.

Now we can write

$$I_t = I_0 - I_a - I_s \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

where I_a and I_s represent the light absorbed and scattered by the colloidal particles in the cell. From the Beer-Lambert law, when absorption is small, and Rayleigh's theory, it follows that

$$I_a = I_0 (KCL) \text{ and } I_s = I_0 h n_0 V_1^2 L$$

where K is the extinction coefficient, C , the concentration of the particles, h is a constant under the conditions of the experiment, V_1 , the volume of a primary particle and n_0 , their number in unit volume of the colloid. Assuming that KCL does not change during coagulation and I'_s , the altered value of I_s after a time, t , from the start of coagulation, we have

$$I_t = I_0 (1 - KCL - hV_r^2 \Sigma n L) \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

where V_r represents the root mean square volume of a particle.

$$\text{Similarly } I_i = I_0 (1 - KCL - LhV_1^2 n_0). \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (7)$$

Substituting D_0 , D_i , and D_t for I_0 , I_i and I_t , respectively, we have from equations (6) and (7)

$$D_t = D_0 (1 - KCL - LhV_r^2 \Sigma n)$$

$$\text{and } D_i = D_0 (1 - KCL - LhV_1^2 n_0).$$

$$\text{Hence. } D_t - D_i = D_0 (LhV_r^2 \Sigma n - LhV_1^2 n_0). \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (8)$$

Assuming that in the region of slow coagulation also, the distribution of particles in different size groups follows the same type of equation as that for rapid coagulation, deduced by Smoluchowski, it can be shown (vide Kruyt, "Colloid Science", 1952, Vol. I, pp. 297-298) that

$$V_r^2 \Sigma n = V_1^2 n_0 (1 + \frac{2t}{T} \epsilon).$$

Substituting this value of $V_r^2 \Sigma n$ in equation (8) and putting γ for $2/T$, we have

$$D_t - D_i = D_0 h L n_0 V_1^2 (1 + \epsilon \gamma t - 1)$$

$$\text{or } 1 - \frac{D_t}{D_i} = \frac{D_0}{D_i} h L n_0 V_1^2 \gamma \epsilon t. \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (9)$$

Now substituting $K/(1 + at)$ for ϵ , as discussed previously, in equation (9), we have

$$\frac{D_t}{D_i} = 1 - \frac{K_1 t}{1 + at} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (10)$$

where $K_1 = \frac{D_0}{D_i} h L n_0 V_1^2 \gamma K$ and is a constant under the conditions of the experiments.

Equation (10) can also be put in the form :

$$\frac{D_t}{D_i} = \frac{1 + (a - K_1)t}{1 + at} = \frac{1 + bt}{1 + at} \quad \dots \quad (11)$$

where $b = (a - K_1)$ and is a constant. It is evident that b may have a positive or a negative value depending on the values of a and K_1 .

In Table II $D_{t\text{obs}}$ represents the observed values and $D_{t\text{calc}}$, those calculated from equation (11) from the corresponding values of t and known values of D_i , and the values of b and a , found from two values of D_t observed and the corresponding values of t . It will be noticed that the agreement between the observed and the calculated values of D_t is quite good.

DISCUSSION

It will be noticed from the data recorded in Table I that the agreement between the observed values Σn and those calculated from equation (4) is fair except in one or two cases. An examination of the experimental data of Kruyt and Van Arkel (*loc. cit.*) will show that erratic value of the number of particles is sometimes obtained in ultramicroscopic counting. Thus for sol 17C containing 50 mM/litre of KCl at $t = 0.66$ hrs., $\Sigma n_{\text{obs}} = 20.9 \times 10^9$ may be one such erratic value. For the same sol containing 60mM/litre of KCl, the observed value of Σn at $t = 49.5$ hrs. is 5.6. Since the original sol contains 29.7×10^9 particles per c.c., it is obvious that the average aggregates consist of nearly 6 primary particles at this stage. Hence, there should then be many aggregates in the sol which should consist of more than 6 primary particles. As the radius of the primary particles is 5.2×10^{-6} cm, therefore these big aggregates of radius greater than 3×10^{-5} cm will begin to settle down and will net smaller particles in the process, leading to a lower value of Σn . Thus, from this stage onward, there is bound to be divergence between the observed and the calculated values of Σn .

It will appear from Table II that the values of D_t (observed) agree well with the corresponding values of D_t (calculated) from equation (11). It may, however, be mentioned that although equation (11) is of the same form as equation (4), and both are deduced from Smoluchowski's equation for slow coagulation on the assumption that $\kappa = K/(1+at)$, yet they differ in one respect, namely, that the constant b in equation (11) may have a negative value. In fact, for the arsenious sulphide sol containing NaCl of strength $N/11$, b has actually a small negative value, -0.003 . This difference between the equations (4) and (11) is to be attributed to the fact that they have been suitably adapted for test by different methods. It may therefore be concluded that equation (4) agrees fairly with the experimental data, while equation (11) does so satisfactorily.

Since the assumption, that in slow coagulation κ decreases with time, leads to useful deductions, attempt should be made to correlate it with some of the factors which change with progress of coagulation. The most obvious one is the average size of the particles. According to Verwey and Overbeek ("Theory of the Stability

of Lyophobic Colloids", 1948, p. 177) the stability of a sol in the presence of an electrolyte (uni-univalent), provided that its concentration is low, say about 27 mM/litre, should increase with the radius of the particles up to about 2×10^{-5} cm, after which it should decrease sharply. The experimental data recorded in Tables I and II, on the other hand, indicate that the rate factor of coagulation decreases with time even when the concentration of the added electrolyte is of the order of $N/15$. There is, thus, some difficulty in the way of correlating k with the energy of repulsion between two interacting particles through their average radius. For the elucidation of the problem further quantitative work is obviously necessary.

In conclusion the author takes the opportunity of expressing his sincere thanks to Mr. K. C. Basak, Director, Economic Research Section, Indian Central Jute Committee, for his helpful criticism.

DEPARTMENT OF PHYSICAL CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY,
CALCUTTA 9.

Received May 15, 1958.